

The Relationship Between Childhood Trauma and Antisocial Behavior in Young Adulthood in Peshawar, Pakistan

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***Objective:** Childhood trauma is a well-established risk factor for adverse psychological outcomes, yet its relationship with antisocial behavior remains underexplored in non-Western, collectivist contexts such as Pakistan. This study examined the association between childhood trauma and antisocial behavior among young individuals aged 16–25 years in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. A cross-sectional, correlational design was employed. A convenience sample of 200 participants (78.5% female; mean age = 20.4 years, SD = 2.7) was recruited from the University of Peshawar and the general population. Participants completed the*

Keywords: Childhood Trauma, Antisocial Behavior, Adverse Childhood Experiences, Young Adults, Pakistan, Trauma-Informed Care, Moderation Analysis

Introduction

Measure	1	2
1. CTQ-SF Total	—	.304**
2. ABS-A Total	.304**	—

HYPERLINK "https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/child-maltreatment"

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